

Human Resource Management Practices impacting on Turnover Intention: Evidence from IT Employees in Bangladesh

Md Kamruzzaman

Department of Business Administration, Multimedia University, 63000, Cyberjaya, Malaysia

Md Abdur Rauf

Project Management Trainer, Center for Policy and Project Management, Dhaka, Bangladesh
raufshiblu@gmail.com

Dr Md Mahfuzul Islam Shamim

Project management professional and public policy practitioner in Bangladesh
myshamim2006@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Organisations' most valuable resource is their human resources, and keeping excellent workers on board is essential for those looking to gain a competitive edge. Organisations use a variety of human resource management (HRM) strategies to control employee churn. The term "Generation Y" refers to the particular generation, often known as the "millennial" or "Internet generation," that was born between the 1980s and the early 1990s. This research investigates the connection between generation Y employee turnover intention and HRM practices. The HRM practices included in the study are perceived training, compensation, performance appraisal, and turnover intention since they are seen to be the key practices with the most effects on an organisation's success. In Bangladesh's private sector, Gen Y's inclination to leave the job is a serious issue.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 22 Jun 2022

Received in revised form

23 Jul 2022

Accepted 31 Aug 2022

Keywords: Human Resource Management Practices, Perceived Training, Compensation, Performance Appraisal, Turnover Intention, Generation Y, Bangladesh.

© 2022 Hosting by Research Parks. All rights reserved.

As a result, information for this study was gathered via a survey of Gen Y workers in Bangladesh, especially in the Dhaka metropolitan region. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), a statistical data analysis program version 25, is used to analyse the association between HRM practices and Gen Y turnover intention. The convenience sampling approach is employed to gather the study sample. The study concludes with suggestions for further research, empirical data for scholarly investigation, and advice on how firms may apply the HRM strategies that can be utilised to manage Gen Y workers to decrease their desire to leave their jobs.

Background of the study

Employee turnover is a significant problem for any business (Kuo, Jou, & Lin, 2012). 59% of Bangladesh's population is considered to be under 29. In 2015, the unemployment rate for those aged 20 to 29 was still relatively high, at more than 39% (Labrague, Gloe, McEnroe-Petite, Tsaras, & Colet, 2018). Bangladesh's economic development, cultural traditions, and young population are said to produce five distinct challenges, including a lack of competitive and satisfying jobs in the private sector, reliance on foreign labour, high youth unemployment, ineffective job matching, and a low rate of female participation in the workforce. According to De Cuyper, Mauno, Kinnunen, and Mäkikangas (2011) and Kumar (2012), these challenging labor market circumstances are associated with increased stress and job anxiety, and poor work-related outcomes. According to a meta-analysis on the relationship between work uneasiness and potential consequences, there are both short- and long-term negative impacts on both employees and employers, and job uncertainty also increases the likelihood that people would leave their jobs (Choi, Pang, Cheung, & Wong, 2011).

Employee turnover is expected and has grown to be a key worry for every firm (Kumar & Singh, 2012). For instance, during the academic year 1997–1998 in the United States of America (U.S.A.), 7.7% of the full-time professors employed by different universities and colleges left their positions to work at other organisations (Shih, Jiang, Klein, & Wang, 2011). Only 29% of these faculty members were retirees; the remaining 71% are members of generation Y who left their universities for various reasons (Chen et al., 2015). According to a recent estimate, in Bangladesh, over 20,000 professionals will leave their jobs in search of better opportunities in Western nations like the United States, Canada, Germany, and the United Kingdom in 2016. These professionals include medical professionals and teaching staff from various universities and colleges (Alom, Patwary, & Khan, 2019).

Numerous variables have been proposed to explain the causes of workers leaving their organisations due to their ubiquity and negative impacts on both people and organisations (Labrague, Gloe, McEnroe-Petite, et al., 2018; Rahman & Iqbal, 2013; Rahman, 2020; Russell, 1997; Yi, Natarajan, & Gong, 2011). Researchers have found that HRM procedures might impact an employee's desire to leave their job (Alom et al., 2019; Manlove & Guzell, 1997; McKnight, Phillips, & Hardgrave, 2009; Takase, 2010). This study investigates which human resource practices influence Generation Y employees' job satisfaction, commitment to the organisation, and intention to quit as well as how different types of organisations are affected by turnover. It does this by considering Generation Y employees' circumstances and their intention to leave.

To formulate a problem statement for this study, gaps in the industry and the literature have been found. Three difficulties with turnover intentions are connected to industry disparities. They are as follows: Employee turnover has been demonstrated to influence costs and the efficiency of private organisations significantly, and generation Y turnover in Bangladeshi private organisations is exceptionally high (Rahman & Iqbal, 2013). Given the high incidence of staff turnover in private businesses in

Bangladesh, it is unavoidably stated in several literary works that expenses and operations have a detrimental impact on private companies. Labrague, Gloe and McEnroe-Petitte, et al., (2018) noted the detrimental effects of staff turnover. The costs of adverse impacts include direct costs, such as lost production, training, selection, and hiring, and indirect costs, such as morale damage, workload impact, and performance disruption. Replacement, and financial and non-financial consequences are additional adverse effects of employee turnover. Time and labour expenditures, material and equipment expenses, cash outlays, and productivity losses make up the majority of the financial costs. The other costs are less obvious and more challenging to assess. Still, they might significantly influence an organisation's ability to function, such as impaired morale and lost business (Kaymakçı, Görener, & Toker, 2022).

In addition to the aforementioned industrial gaps, there appear to be two major research gaps regarding turnover intention, namely: a. the dearth of high-quality research on Generation Y employees' turnover intentions; and b. the fact that the majority of recent studies on turnover intention are restricted to Generation Y in western countries. The intention of Bangladeshi Generation Y workers has never been recognised as a research sample, despite several studies linking HR activities to employee turnover (Akgunduz & Eryilmaz, 2018; Califf & Brooks, 2020; Jensen, 2021; Kaymakçı et al., 2022; Mao, He, Liu, Zhang, & Zhu, 2018; Xu, Tao, Huang, Little, & Huang, 2020). However, there is a dearth of empirical research on the effect of HRM policies on generation Y workers' desire to leave their jobs in Bangladeshi organisations (Kim & Shim, 2018; Liao, Widowati, Hu, & Tasman, 2017; Yang Yang, Liu, Liu, & Zhang, 2015). "Although there have been studies on the intention to leave a job, the literature evaluation for this study has not yet turned up any studies that particularly emphasise Generation Y workers. Employers and HR professionals must know the strategies to adopt to keep Gen Y employees and their skills (Abid, Zahra, & Ahmed, 2016). Since the organisational duty is a significant antecedent of turnover, Emiroğlu, Akova, and Tanrıverdi (2015) suggests that understanding the characteristics of the different generations is essential in determining the most effective strategies for lowering change resistance among workers. As a result, few studies on the variables that influence generation Y workers' intentions to leave their jobs. However, this situation seriously jeopardises the operations and financial health of Bangladeshi private companies. The additional issue in this research is to determine if salary, performance assessment, and training and development procedures have any meaningful impact on the desire of Bangladeshi Generation Y workers to leave their private organisations.

Human Resource Practices and Turnover

Recently, researchers have suggested that organisational practices that demonstrate an interest in workers and their growth ought to lower organisational turnover. Akova, Cetin, and Cifci, (2015) for instance, argued that high-performance work practices that support employee growth or motivation (such as internal promotion and labour-management participation teams) should improve retention and discovered evidence to support this claim. These practices also appeared to correlate with organisational turnover rates negatively. Similar to this, Back, Hyun, Jeung, and Chang (2020) proposed that organisational quit rates should be decreased by HR policies that signify investments in human capital (such as pay and benefits systems) or are designed to increase commitment (such as procedural fairness, and participation).

Although there is evidence that certain HR practices at the organisational level are related to organisational turnover rates, assuming that perceptions of these practices at the individual level are similarly related to individual turnover decisions would be an ecological fallacy (Chen, Li, Li, Lyu, & Zhang, 2018). Election results and party membership in a voting district are two examples of relationships at one level of aggregation that may not hold at another level (e.g., individual party

membership and vote in a particular election). According to Mao et al., (2018), clarifying the connection between these corporate HR policies and disengagement at the personal level is crucial.

There is no evidence connecting these HR procedures to judgments about individual turnover. According to Li and Yao, (2022), reward fairness, engagement, and views of development prospects had only marginally negative impacts on turnover; these behaviours may be a little distal predictor of turnover, as shown by the impacts' modest amplitude. Many turnover antecedents, such as work qualities, may be psychologically farther out or more distal from turnover, with implications that are mediated by closer or more proximal factors, (e.g., turnover intentions).

Perceived Training and Turnover Intention

According to earlier theoretical research, the impact of training on people's voluntary turnover can be either positive or negative depending on whether employees receive training in specific or general skills, how much each employee pays for training, the firms' expectations for employee turnover, and the practices of rival firms (Park & Min, 2020). Recent initiatives have attempted to pinpoint the underlying psychological factors (Vui-Yee & Yen-Hwa, 2020; Zhang, Ma, Xu, & Xu, 2019; Zhu, Cai, Buchtel, & Guan, 2019). Studies examining and evaluating such psychological systems' effects are still lacking, nevertheless (Asghar et al., 2021; Califf & Brooks, 2020; Xu et al., 2020).

According to studies, a person's intrinsic motivation for learning is a significant psychological factor that positively influences employee outcomes, including productivity, dedication, and turnover (Park & Min, 2020). Following this research, training expectations are defined to consider people's interest in training. We broadly look at employer-sponsored training, including in-house Training, on-the-job Training, formal and informal Training, coaching, and mentoring. Three elements of training that are significant to workers can be pinpointed via our assessment of the literature: training content, operational variables, and results (Reza et al., 2021; Shamim, 2017). Training materials provide information and abilities that may be used in the workplace. People often anticipate learning job-specific competencies necessary for the performance and company-specific standards and guidelines to make it easier for them to operate inside the firm (Kazemi, Shapiro, & Kavner, 2015). Additionally, they want to learn skills that will help them get a job (Tongchaiprasit & Ariyabuddhipongs, 2016). As a comprehensive phrase, including the design, organisation, and execution of training, we use "operational factors" to refer to elements like training providers, duration, support, and so forth. The operation of training influences learners' responses and behaviour, according to studies on training efficacy (Chen et al., 2015). Jiang, Wang, Chu, and Zheng (2019) found that when assessing workers' preferences for training alternatives, they tended to demand skilled trainers, well-regarded training providers, and sponsorship of training fees.

Additionally, the literature suggests that most learners anticipate a respectable amount of training time (Yim, Seo, Cho, & Kim, 2017). Organisational assistance as a key element in training operations. Employers' financial support and peer cohesiveness are examples of organisational assistance (Lyu, Ji, Zheng, Yu, & Fan, 2019). Employees often desire a friendly environment where they may get encouragement and feedback from managers and colleagues (Alom et al., 2019; W. Jiang et al., 2019; Labrague, Gloe, McEnroe-Petitte, et al., 2018; Mao et al., 2018). Additionally, it was shown that workers often anticipated post-training tutoring since it helped them use their learned abilities at work (Kim & Shim, 2018). We do not want to discuss the cost and performance elements of organisational training, given the particular emphasis of this research. Instead, we look at how staff members assess the training they get. Therefore,

H1: There is a significant relationship between Perceived Training and Turnover Intention of Generation Y employees in Bangladesh

Compensation and Turnover Intention

A sort of remuneration or incentive provided to an employee as a consequence of their labour is known as compensation (Labrague, McEnroe – Petite, et al., 2018). Unsatisfactory pay, significant demand from other companies, shift work, and unclear employment status may all contribute to the desire to leave a present employer (Li, Zhang, Xiao, Chen, & Lu, 2019). A person's pay may be good or unsatisfactory depending on how it compares to what others got. Satisfaction with pay will reduce absenteeism and employee desire to leave (Vui-Yee & Yen-Hwa, 2020). Yuanyuan Yang and Chen, (2020) added that an inadequate wage influences the desire to leave a job.

According to earlier research, workers' desire to leave their jobs is significantly influenced by their incentive and retention strategies (Alom et al., 2019; Lyu et al., 2019; Yin, Bi, & Ni, 2022; Zhou, Li, & Gao, 2020). Competitive compensation encourages employees to remain committed to their employers. The feeling of responsibility for the work assigned to the employees will also rise with proper remuneration appropriate for duty (Califf & Brooks, 2020). Although empirical research has shown that compensation is one of the most crucial factors for determining an employee's job retention, which in turn reduces the intention to leave their job early, the fact remains that various measures are used to balance the effort of the employees at their various positions. As a result, it can be hypothesised that:

H2: Compensation practices have a significant impact on the employee turnover intention of Generation Y employees in Bangladesh

Performance Appraisal and Turnover Intention

An important aspect of managing human resources in firms is performance appraisal (PA) (Li et al., 2019; Park & Min, 2020). The processes and procedures used by businesses to evaluate their personnel's performance level are referred to as performance assessment (or performance evaluation) (Akgunduz & Eryilmaz, 2018; Jiang et al., 2019; Vui-Yee & Yen-Hwa, 2020; Zhu et al., 2019). This procedure often entails evaluating workers' performance and giving feedback on the performance's intensity and calibre (Bianchi, 2016; I.-J. Kim & Shim, 2018).

An in-depth examination by Shahpouri, Namdari, and Abedi (2016) further shows that formal performance assessment systems appeal because they are capable of various duties. These duties might include keeping an eye on employees, informing workers of organisational values and goals, assessing recruiting and training plans, and confirming other HRM procedures (Abid et al., 2016). Alom et al., (2019) asserts that performance appraisal is embraced when a company anticipates advantages from implementing HRM techniques. According to this theory, the employer must choose not only if it is worthwhile to establish a formal system of performance review but also how it will be structured to produce results (Mao et al., 2018).

According to earlier studies, the formal method of watching and assessing an employee's performance is known as performance assessment (Chung, Jung, & Sohn, 2017; Jiang & Shen, 2018; Labrague, Gloe, McEnroe, Konstantinos, & Colet, 2018; Li, Kim, & Zhao, 2017; Zhu et al., 2019). Jiang et al., (2019) listed the following objectives for performance evaluation: Giving workers feedback on their performance, enabling choices regarding raises in salary, promotions, and layoffs, promoting performance improvement, defining and evaluating objectives, and deciding on both individual and

organisational training and development are all examples of good management. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H3: Performance Appraisals have a significant impact on employee turnover intention

Theoretical framework and Proposed Models

The suggested research model was examined in this study using the following ideas as a theoretical point of view. Notably, the critical lens employed to operationalise and comprehend the link between the variables is social exchange theory (SET). The foundation of SET is the notion that people's economic and social behaviour results from an exchange process (Blau, 1968; Eisenberger, Stinglhamber, Vandenberghe, Sucharski, & Rhoades, 2002). This exchange procedure's primary goal is to maximise advantages and reduce expenses (Takase, 2010). SET is mainly used to forecast the parties' interactions and communications that will result in long-lasting relationships (Eisenberger et al., 2002). The transaction might be viewed in tangible and non-material items, such as the emblems of acceptance or status. According to the literature, researchers often examine the interaction between the parties, including workers and employers, from the SET viewpoint (Blau, 1968). It is because the SET, like anything else, has outcomes like pleasure and connection reliance (Alom et al., 2019; Jang & George, 2012; Kuo et al., 2012; Shih et al., 2011). Offering appealing HRM procedures demonstrates a company's desire to have a social exchange connection with its personnel (Snape and Redman, 2010). Individuals will then reciprocate in good ways by exhibiting positive attitudes, including more significant organisational commitment and staying choices, which eventually benefit the organisation following the reciprocity norm (McKnight et al., 2009). This research suggests that HRM policies may affect Generation Y employees' inclinations to leave their jobs using SET. This study also intends to further SET by providing insight into using SET as the primary framework for analysing Generation Y employee turnover intentions and HRM practices. (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: Research Model

Method

Sample and Procedures

For this study, a simple random sample approach was used. The Generation Y workforce in Dhaka city makes up the target demographic. The Federation of Bangladesh Chambers of Commerce and Industry (FBCCI), the association of private enterprises in Bangladesh, has 458 active private organisations listed as of July 2019. As of 2019, these organisations employ over 25000 young people, or generation Y workers (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, 2020). The data was provided by a sample of 132 Generation Y workers from Dhaka-based private companies. With a total of 88 (66.7%) male and 44

(33.3%) female respondents, this research demonstrates that the proportion of male respondents is much more significant than that of female respondents. With 74 responses, the age range of 25–39 years has the highest percentage of respondents (56.1%), followed by the age range of 30–34 years (28.0%) with 37 respondents. With 13 and 08 respondents representing 9.80% and 06.1%, the age categories 20–24 years and 35–38 years had the fewest responses. Approximately 98% of the respondents in this research are between the ages of 20 and 38.

Measures

The constructs of perceived training, compensation, and performance appraisal were measured using the items developed by Guchait (2007), while the construct of turnover intention was measured using the items of Mahesar (2015). All the items in the questionnaire created for this study had already been used and tested. English was used for the questionnaire since it is a worldwide language in this research. All items included in this questionnaire have been measured using a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree and 5 =strongly agree).

Findings

Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum score were used to describe the observed variables (See table 1).

Table 1: Means, Standard Deviations,

	Perceived Training	Compensation	Performance	Perceived Training
Mean	3.3015	3.1955	3.2083	3.1837
Std. Deviation	0.63510	0.68861	0.72521	0.62917

The reliability of the data was assessed using Cronbach's alpha to produce internal consistency reliability scores. A method for assessing a scale's internal consistency is the reliability test. Levels of consistency have been measured using Cronbach's alpha. All variables and constructs need to have Cronbach's alpha values better than 0.6. A scale's Cronbach's alpha coefficient may be accepted if it is more than 0.6, according to Nunnally (1978). All the notions and elements taken into account for the empirical inquiry must be supported via the usage of reliability and validity evaluation (Hair & Alamer, 2022). For this empirical study, reliability and validity indicators reveal how completely the data have been objectively investigated. According to Field (2013), reliability is the process of choosing a measuring instrument so that it should consistently reflects the construct being assessed. The reliability and accuracy of the whole study will be ensured by the data's consistency, adding to the body of knowledge. Sekaran and Bougie (2016) states that dependability allows for evaluating validity and reliability (see table 2).

Table 2: Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha)

Variable/Construct	Cronbach's α	Number of items
Perceived Training	0.913	5
Compensation	0.842	5
Performance Appraisal	0.873	4
urnover Intention	0.788	4

Multiple Regression applications are often used in psychology to test a hypothesis regarding causal factors on the result measure (Waseem, Rashid, Warraich, Sadiq, & Shaukat, 2018). Given its versatility, multiple regression appeals to academics (Piers, Versluys, Devoghel, Vyt, & Van Den

Noortgate, 2019). It may be used to analyse relationships between pairs of variables while accounting for possible confounding factors, test the linear connection between variable hypotheses, and test complicated associations among several variables (Çamveren, Kocaman, & Vatan, 2022)(See table 3).

Table 3: Regression Analysis

	Hypothesis	Standardised	t value	p value	Collinearity	
		Coefficients			Tolerance	VIF
		Beta				
H1	Perceived training > Turnover Intention	0.258	4.677	0.000	0.543	1.840
H2	Compensation > Turnover Intention	0.013	0.229	0.819	0.363	2.757
H3	Performance Appraisal > Turnover Intention	0.526	8.196	0.000	0.532	1.878

Note: *p* value: <0.05

Discussion

For instance, during the academic year 1997–1998 in the United States of America (U.S.A.), 7.7% of the full-time professors employed by different universities and colleges left their positions to work at other organisations. Only 29% of these faculty members were retirees; the remaining 71% are members of generation Y who left their universities for various reasons (Pousette et al., 2014). According to a recent estimate, in Bangladesh, over 20,000 professionals will leave their jobs in search of better opportunities in Western nations like the United States, Canada, Germany, and the United Kingdom in 2016. These professionals include medical professionals and teaching staff from various universities and colleges (Mao et al., 2018).

Numerous variables have been proposed to explain the causes of workers leaving their organisations due to their ubiquity and negative impacts on both people and organisations (Arshadi & Shahbazi, 2013; Emiroğlu et al., 2015; Kazemi et al., 2015; Lotfi, Akhuleh, Judi, & Khodayari, 2022). Researchers have found that HRM procedures might impact an employee's desire to leave their job (Long, Ajagbe, & Kowang, 2014; Mahesar, 2015). This study investigates which human resource practices influence Generation Y employees' job satisfaction, commitment to the organisation, and intention to quit as well as how different types of organisations are affected by turnover. It does this by considering Generation Y employees' circumstances and their intention to leave.

To formulate a problem statement for this study, gaps in the industry and the literature have been found. Three difficulties with turnover intentions are connected to industry disparities. They are as follows: Employee turnover has been demonstrated to influence costs and the efficiency of private organisations significantly, and generation Y turnover in Bangladeshi private organisations is exceptionally high. Given the high incidence of staff turnover in private businesses in Bangladesh, it is unavoidably stated in several literary works that expenses and operations have a detrimental impact on private companies. Kim and Shim (2018) noted the damaging effects of staff turnover. The costs of adverse impacts include direct costs, such as lost production, training, selection, and hiring, and indirect costs, such as

morale damage, workload impact, and performance disruption. Separation, replacement and financial and non-financial consequences are additional negative effects of employee turnover. Time and labour expenditures, material and equipment expenses, cash outlays, and productivity losses make up most of the financial costs. The other costs are less obvious and more challenging to assess, but they might have a major detrimental influence on an organisation's ability to function, such as impaired morale and lost business (Labrague, Gloe, McEnroe, et al., 2018; Labrague, Gloe, McEnroe-Petitte, et al., 2018).

In addition to the aforementioned industrial gaps, there appear to be two major research gaps regarding turnover intention, namely: a. the dearth of high-quality research on Generation Y employees' turnover intentions; and b. the fact that the majority of recent studies on turnover intention are restricted to Generation Y in western countries. The intention of Bangladeshi Generation Y workers has never been recognised as a research sample, despite several studies linking HR activities to employee turnover. However, there is a dearth of empirical research on the effect of HRM policies on generation Y workers' desire to leave their jobs in Bangladeshi organisations (Kim & Kao, 2014; Kim & Shim, 2018; Takase, 2010). "Although there have been studies on the intention to leave a job, the literature evaluation for this study has not yet turned up any studies that particularly emphasise Generation Y workers. Employers and HR professionals must know the strategies to adopt to keep Gen Y employees and their skills (Li, Guo, & Zhou, 2021; Yuanyuan Yang & Chen, 2020). Since organisational duty is a significant antecedent of turnover, Kazemi et al., (2015) suggests that understanding the characteristics of the different generations is essential in determining the most effective strategies for lowering change resistance among workers. As a result, few studies on the variables that influence generation Y workers' intentions to leave their jobs. However, this situation seriously jeopardises the operations and financial health of Bangladeshi private companies. The additional issue in this research is to determine if salary, performance assessment, and training and development procedures have any meaningful impact on the desire of Bangladeshi Generation Y workers to leave their private organisations.

Implications

According to the study's findings, HRM practices and intention to turnover have a significant association. The study's conclusions are quite important for the management of private organisations in Bangladesh to comprehend the purpose of Generation Y employees to leave their jobs. The research investigated how generation Y workers see the significance of HRM practices such as salary, job security, performance reviews, and training and development when they decide to have a turnover intention. The business now uses these full HRM practices as vital instruments to help with its strategic management.

The generation Y workforce in private organisations is typically concerned with all HRM practices as a consequence of the obtained results, demonstrating a significant association between independent factors and the desire to leave. In addition, the management of private Bangladeshi firms must understand the significance of HRM practices since they significantly impact the intention to turnover staff. The organisation's HRM practices may be reviewed by management to improve them. It is due to the survey's findings, which indicate that most generation Y workers are dissatisfied with existing HRM practices like the remuneration offered by the company.

To develop a solution to lessen the intention of turnover, managers in Bangladeshi firms must pay attention to generation Y personnel. To establish and set clear, fair, and achievable objectives for the workers of that particular age group, management may meet with or consult with generation Y personnel. Moreover, this study gave private businesses in Bangladesh the chance to alter HRM procedures and lessen the likelihood of turnover. The study will make academics more devoted to them

and help them maintain their reputation in the increasingly competitive sector. Employee productivity and effectiveness will immediately rise when firms successfully motivate their workforce.

Limitations and future research

Since most notable private organisations are concentrated in this area, our analysis has primarily focused on Dhaka City. Future studies should be done on all sectors in the nation and the variables influencing employee turnover intentions across all age groups. Before performing this survey, the entire Generation Y workforce was undocumented. The researchers will need to track down the precise numerical data on Generation Y for future study. The organisation will be more stable if turnover intentions are lower.

References

1. Abid, G., Zahra, I., & Ahmed, A. (2016). Promoting thriving at work and waning turnover intention: A relational perspective. *Future Business Journal*, 2(2), 127-137. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2016.08.001>
2. Akgunduz, Y., & Eryilmaz, G. (2018). Does turnover intention mediate the effects of job insecurity and co-worker support on social loafing? *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 68, 41-49. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2017.09.010>
3. Akova, O., Cetin, G., & Cifci, I. (2015). The Relation between Demographic Factors and the Turnover Intention in Pre-opening Hotel Businesses. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 207, 377-384. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.10.177>
4. Alom, S., Patwary, A., & Khan, M. (2019). Factors affecting the turnover intention of Bangladeshi migrants in the United Arab Emirates: An empirical study on the hotel industry. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity Change*, 8(3), 344-360.
5. Arshadi, N., & Shahbazi, F. (2013). Workplace Characteristics and Turnover Intention: Mediating Role of Emotional Exhaustion. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 84, 640-645. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.06.618>
6. Asghar, M., Tayyab, M., Gull, N., Zhijie, S., Shi, R., & Tao, X. (2021). Polychronicity, work engagement, and turnover intention: The moderating role of perceived organizational support in the hotel industry. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 49, 129-139. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2021.09.004>
7. Back, C.-Y., Hyun, D.-S., Jeung, D.-Y., & Chang, S.-J. (2020). Mediating Effects of Burnout in the Association Between Emotional Labor and Turnover Intention in Korean Clinical Nurses. *Safety and Health at Work*, 11(1), 88-96. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2020.01.002>
8. Bianchi, R. (2016). Occupational and non-occupational strains should be concomitantly considered in research on burnout, organizational commitment, and turnover intention. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 53, 403-404. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2015.10.005>
9. Blau, P. M. (1968). Social exchange. *International encyclopedia of the social sciences*, 7(4), 452-457.
10. Califf, C. B., & Brooks, S. (2020). An empirical study of techno-stressors, literacy facilitation, burnout, and turnover intention as experienced by K-12 teachers. *Computers & Education*, 157, 103971. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103971>

11. Çamveren, H., Kocaman, G., & Vatan, F. (2022). The effects of a preceptorship program on newcomer nurses' turnover intention, commitment and job satisfaction: Quasi-experimental study. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 63, 103358. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2022.103358>
12. Chen, H., Li, G., Li, M., Lyu, L., & Zhang, T. (2018). A cross-sectional study on nurse turnover intention and influencing factors in Jiangsu Province, China. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 5(4), 396-402. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2018.09.012>
13. Chen, M.-L., Su, Z.-Y., Lo, C.-L., Chiu, C.-H., Hu, Y.-H., Shieh, T.-Y., & Lee, H.-E. (2015). Corrigendum to "An empirical study on the factors influencing the turnover intention of dentists in hospitals in Taiwan" [Journal of Dental Sciences 2014;9:332–344]. *Journal of Dental Sciences*, 10(1), 114. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jds.2015.03.001>
14. Choi, S. P.-p., Pang, S. M.-c., Cheung, K., & Wong, T. K.-s. (2011). Stabilizing and destabilizing forces in the nursing work environment: A qualitative study on turnover intention. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 48(10), 1290-1301. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2011.03.005>
15. Chung, E. K., Jung, Y., & Sohn, Y. W. (2017). A moderated mediation model of job stress, job satisfaction, and turnover intention for airport security screeners. *Safety Science*, 98, 89-97. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2017.06.005>
16. De Cuyper, N., Mauno, S., Kinnunen, U., & Mäkikangas, A. (2011). The role of job resources in the relation between perceived employability and turnover intention: A prospective two-sample study. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 78(2), 253-263. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2010.09.008>
17. Eisenberger, R., Stinglhamber, F., Vandenberghe, C., Sucharski, I. L., & Rhoades, L. (2002). Perceived supervisor support: contributions to perceived organizational support and employee retention. *Journal of applied psychology*, 87(3), 565.
18. Emiroğlu, B. D., Akova, O., & Tanrıverdi, H. (2015). The Relationship Between Turnover Intention and Demographic Factors in Hotel Businesses: A Study at Five Star Hotels in Istanbul. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 207, 385-397. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.10.108>
19. Field, A. (2013). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics*: sage.
20. Guchait, P. (2007). *Human resource management practices and organizational commitment and intention to leave: The mediating role of perceived organizational support and psychological contracts*: University of Missouri-Columbia.
21. Hair, J., & Alamer, A. (2022). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) in second language and education research: Guidelines using an applied example. *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*, 1(3), 100027. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmal.2022.100027>
22. Jang, J., & George, R. T. (2012). Understanding the influence of polychronicity on job satisfaction and turnover intention: A study of non-supervisory hotel employees. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 31(2), 588-595. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2011.08.004>
23. Jensen, M. T. (2021). Pupil-teacher ratio, disciplinary problems, classroom emotional climate, and turnover intention: Evidence from a randomized control trial. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 105, 103415. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103415>
24. Jiang, H., & Shen, H. (2018). Supportive organizational environment, work-life enrichment, trust and turnover intention: A national survey of PRSA membership. *Public Relations Review*, 44(5),

681-689. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2018.08.007>

25. Jiang, W., Wang, L., Chu, Z., & Zheng, C. (2019). Does leader turnover intention hinder team innovation performance? The roles of leader self-sacrificial behavior and empathic concern. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, 261-270. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.013>
26. Kaymakçı, R., Görener, A., & Toker, K. (2022). The perceived overqualification's effect on innovative work behaviour: Do transformational leadership and turnover intention matter? *Current Research in Behavioral Sciences*, 3, 100068. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbeha.2022.100068>
27. Kazemi, E., Shapiro, M., & Kavner, A. (2015). Predictors of intention to turnover in behavior technicians working with individuals with autism spectrum disorder. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 17, 106-115. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2015.06.012>
28. Kim, H., & Kao, D. (2014). A meta-analysis of turnover intention predictors among U.S. child welfare workers. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 47, 214-223. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2014.09.015>
29. Kim, I.-J., & Shim, H.-W. (2018). Subjectivity About Turnover Intention Among Male Nurses in South Korea: A Q-Methodological Study. *Asian Nursing Research*, 12(2), 113-120. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anr.2018.04.002>
30. Kumar, M. (2012). Roles of Perceived Exchange Quality and Organisational Identification in Predicting Turnover Intention. *IIMB Management Review*, 24(1), 2. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2012.01.005>
31. Kumar, M., & Singh, S. (2012). Roles of perceived exchange quality and organisational identification in predicting turnover intention. *IIMB Management Review*, 24(1), 5-15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2011.12.005>
32. Kuo, C.-W., Jou, R.-C., & Lin, S.-W. (2012). Turnover intention of air traffic controllers in Taiwan: A note. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 25, 50-52. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2012.08.003>
33. Labrague, L. J., Gloe, D., McEnroe, D. M., Konstantinos, K., & Colet, P. (2018). Factors influencing turnover intention among registered nurses in Samar Philippines. *Applied Nursing Research*, 39, 200-206. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr.2017.11.027>
34. Labrague, L. J., Gloe, D. S., McEnroe-Petitte, D. M., Tsaras, K., & Colet, P. C. (2018). Erratum to “Factors influencing turnover intention among registered nurses in Samar, Philippines” [Applied Nursing Research 39C (2018) 200–206]. *Applied Nursing Research*, 41, 86. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr.2018.03.006>
35. Labrague, L. J., McEnroe – Petitte, D. M., Tsaras, K., Cruz, J. P., Colet, P. C., & Gloe, D. S. (2018). Organizational commitment and turnover intention among rural nurses in the Philippines: Implications for nursing management. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 5(4), 403-408. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2018.09.001>
36. Li, J., Kim, W. G., & Zhao, X. (2017). Multilevel model of management support and casino employee turnover intention. *Tourism Management*, 59, 193-204. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2016.08.006>
37. Li, N., Zhang, L., Xiao, G., Chen, J., & Lu, Q. (2019). The relationship between workplace

- violence, job satisfaction and turnover intention in emergency nurses. *International Emergency Nursing*, 45, 50-55. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ienj.2019.02.001>
38. Li, R., & Yao, M. (2022). What promotes teachers' turnover intention? Evidence from a meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 37, 100477. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2022.100477>
39. Li, X., Guo, Y., & Zhou, S. (2021). Chinese preschool teachers' income, work-family conflict, organizational commitment, and turnover intention: A serial mediation model. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 128, 106005. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2021.106005>
40. Liao, S.-h., Widowati, R., Hu, D.-c., & Tasman, L. (2017). The mediating effect of psychological contract in the relationships between paternalistic leadership and turnover intention for foreign workers in Taiwan. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 22(2), 80-87. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2016.08.003>
41. Long, C. S., Ajagbe, M. A., & Kowang, T. O. (2014). Addressing the Issues on Employees' Turnover Intention in the Perspective of HRM Practices in SME. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 129, 99-104. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.03.653>
42. Lotfi, M., Akhuleh, O. Z., Judi, A., & Khodayari, M. (2022). Turnover intention among operating room nurses during the COVID-19 outbreak and its association with perceived safety climate. *Perioperative Care and Operating Room Management*, 26, 100233. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcorn.2021.100233>
43. Lyu, D., Ji, L., Zheng, Q., Yu, B., & Fan, Y. (2019). Abusive supervision and turnover intention: Mediating effects of psychological empowerment of nurses. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 6(2), 198-203. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2018.12.005>
44. Mahesar, H. A. (2015). The impact of HRM bundles and organisational commitment on managers turnover intentions.
45. Manlove, E. E., & Guzell, J. R. (1997). Intention to leave, anticipated reasons for leaving, and 12-month turnover of child care center staff. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 12(2), 145-167. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2006\(97\)90010-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2006(97)90010-7)
46. Mao, Y., He, R., Liu, J., Zhang, N., & Zhu, B. (2018). Turnover intention of primary health workers in China: a systematic review. *The Lancet*, 392, S17. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)32646-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32646-1)
47. McKnight, D. H., Phillips, B., & Hardgrave, B. C. (2009). Which reduces IT turnover intention the most: Workplace characteristics or job characteristics? *Information & Management*, 46(3), 167-174. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2009.01.002>
48. Nunnally, J. (1978). *Psychometric Theory* 2nd edition (New York: McGraw).
49. Park, J., & Min, H. (2020). Turnover intention in the hospitality industry: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 90, 102599. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102599>
50. Piers, R. D., Versluys, K., Devoghel, J., Vyt, A., & Van Den Noortgate, N. (2019). Interprofessional teamwork, quality of care and turnover intention in geriatric care: A cross-sectional study in 55 acute geriatric units. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 91, 94-100.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2018.11.011>

51. Rahman, M. M., & Iqbal, F. (2013). A comprehensive relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention of private commercial bank employees' in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Science*
52. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 2(6), 17-23.
53. Rahman, S. M. (2020). Relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Asian Business Review*, 10(2), 99-108.
54. Reza, M. N. H., Jayashree, S., Malarvizhi, C. A. N., Rauf, M. A., Jayaraman, K., & Shareef, S. H. (2021). The implications of Industry 4.0 on supply chains amid the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic review. *FResearch*, 10.
55. Russell, S. (1997). Response to "intention to leave, anticipated reasons for leaving, and 12-month turnover of child care center staff". *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 12(2), 171-172. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2006\(97\)90012-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2006(97)90012-0)
56. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*: john wiley & sons.
57. Shahpouri, S., Namdari, K., & Abedi, A. (2016). Mediating role of work engagement in the relationship between job resources and personal resources with turnover intention among female nurses. *Applied Nursing Research*, 30, 216-221. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr.2015.10.008>
58. Shamim, M. I. (2022). Exploring the Success Factors of Project Management. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(7), 64-72.
59. Shamim, M. I. (2017). Leveraging Social Media for Human Resource Development led ICT Sector Development in Bangladesh. *Business Review Bangladesh*, 6(1), 74-85.
60. Shih, S.-P., Jiang, J. J., Klein, G., & Wang, E. (2011). Learning demand and job autonomy of IT personnel: Impact on turnover intention. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27(6), 2301-2307. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2011.07.009>
61. Statistics, B. B. o. (2020). *Statistical Yearbook of Bangladesh*: Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics.
62. Takase, M. (2010). A concept analysis of turnover intention: Implications for nursing management. *Collegian*, 17(1), 3-12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colegn.2009.05.001>
63. Tongchaiprasit, P., & Ariyabuddhiphongs, V. (2016). Creativity and turnover intention among hotel chefs: The mediating effects of job satisfaction and job stress. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 55, 33-40. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2016.02.009>
64. Vui-Yee, K., & Yen-Hwa, T. (2020). When does ostracism lead to turnover intention? The moderated mediation model of job stress and job autonomy. *IIMB Management Review*, 32(3), 238-248. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2019.10.007>
65. Waseem, A., Rashid, Y., Warraich, M. A., Sadiq, I., & Shaukat, Z. (2018). Factors affecting E-commerce potential of any country using multiple regression analysis. *Journal of Internet Banking*
66. *Commerce*, 24(2), 1-28.
67. Xu, S., Tao, L., Huang, H., Little, J., & Huang, L. (2020). Pediatric Nurses' Turnover Intention and

- Its Association with Calling in China's Tertiary Hospitals. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 52, e51-e56. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2020.01.005>
68. Yang, Y., & Chen, J. (2020). Related Factors of Turnover Intention Among Pediatric Nurses in Mainland China: A Structural Equation Modeling Analysis. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 53, e217-e223. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2020.04.018>
69. Yang, Y., Liu, Y.-H., Liu, J.-Y., & Zhang, H.-F. (2015). The impact of work support and organizational career growth on nurse turnover intention in China. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 2(2), 134-139. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2015.04.006>
70. Yi, Y., Natarajan, R., & Gong, T. (2011). Customer participation and citizenship behavioral influences on employee performance, satisfaction, commitment, and turnover intention. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(1), 87-95. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2009.12.007>
71. Yim, H.-Y., Seo, H.-J., Cho, Y., & Kim, J. (2017). Mediating Role of Psychological Capital in Relationship between Occupational Stress and Turnover Intention among Nurses at Veterans Administration Hospitals in Korea. *Asian Nursing Research*, 11(1), 6-12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anr.2017.01.002>
72. Yin, J., Bi, Y., & Ni, Y. (2022). The impact of COVID-19 on turnover intention among hotel employees: A moderated mediation model. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 51, 539-549. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2022.05.010>
73. Zhang, X., Ma, L., Xu, B., & Xu, F. (2019). How social media usage affects employees' job satisfaction and turnover intention: An empirical study in China. *Information & Management*, 56(6), 103136. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2018.12.004>
74. Zhou, S., Li, X., & Gao, B. (2020). Family/friends support, work-family conflict, organizational commitment, and turnover intention in young preschool teachers in China: A serial mediation model. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 113, 104997. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.104997>
75. Zhu, F., Cai, Z., Buchtel, E. E., & Guan, Y. (2019). Career construction in social exchange: a dual-path model linking career adaptability to turnover intention. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 112, 282-293. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2019.04.003>